

Dye-Surfactant Interactions. A Spectral Study†

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LUMINESCENCE, which includes fluorescence, phosphorescence and chemiluminescence, is a very fertile field of research and provides some of the most sensitive methods of analysis. Fluorescence results from a rapid emission of light energy from a molecule which has become excited by the absorption of light. This process tends to be favoured if the compound satisfies the following conditions: (i) the longest wavelength of absorption in uv or visible region corresponds to a $\pi-\pi^*$ transition, (ii) it possesses an excited singlet state which has a half-life of nearly 10^{-8} s, and (iii) it has excited singlet state S, and triplet state T which are well separated.

The structural requirements for fluorescence of an organic compound are based on three main factors, viz. the nature of carbon skeleton, the geometrical arrangement of the molecule, and the type and position of substituents. In addition to the structural factors, environmental factors also affect the fluorescence spectrum of a compound¹; these are pH, temperature, solvent molecule, presence of other molecules, and instrumental factors. Generally it is observed that fluorescing molecules have rigid, non-crowded, planar structure. It can also be expected that if a fluorescing molecule is bounded to a polymer, this would retard intra-molecular twisting, resulting in enhanced fluorescence.

Strongly fluorescent dyes belong to a few classes, of which those derived from the xanthene, acridine, phenazine, diphenylmethane and triphenylmethane groups are the most important². These also display a tendency to aggregate into dimers or oligomers, due to high electric polarisation which becomes prominent at concentrations greater than 10^{-4} M (Ref. 3). The absorption spectra of the majority of organic dyestuffs in aqueous solutions do not obey Beer's law, while it is generally obeyed in alcoholic solution⁴. The deviation from Beer's law has been explained by the hypothesis of reversible dimerisation or polymerisation. The bonding energy in the dissolved state will be the difference between the affinities of the dye molecule for another of its own species and for the solvent. Since the energy of such bond is of the order of thermal energy at room temperature, the influence of concentration on the deviation from Beer's law depends strongly and reversibly on temperature.

The aggregation of dye molecules affect the efficiency of their fluorescence⁵. They also exhibit

metachromic effect during this process, wherein their colour also undergoes change. The metachromic colour appears to return to the original colour at a higher temperature in a reversible manner suggesting a reversible dissociation of the dye aggregate⁶.

Surfactants can be defined as a class of substances which have a tendency to aggregate in solution. Two regions characterise the chemical structure of a surfactant. One is the hydrocarbon chain, while the other is the water-soluble group. The peculiar structure causes the surfactant molecules to aggregate in a unique pattern, when present at above a certain concentration, in water. During the process of aggregation, the hydrophobic part of the molecules remain inside the cluster, avoiding contact with water, while the hydrophilic groups remain outside in contact with the solvent. The clusters thus assume colloidal dimensions which are better known as micelle. Micelle gets easily adsorbed at interfaces and, therefore, such a solution penetrates porous materials, disperses solid particles, emulsifies oil, and produces foam when stirred. The process of micelle formation is assumed to start when the surfactant reaches a certain concentration level in water (better known as critical micelle concentration, cmc). It is also believed that micelles exist in equilibrium with the monomer molecules or ions⁷. Many dyes, polynuclear hydrocarbons, proteins and lipophilic substances are stabilised in presence of micelles, while displaying marked spectral and colour changes^{8,9}.

Observing changes in the fluorescence can be a sensitive way to monitor the interaction between dyes and surfactants. With this end in view, the following groups of dyes were selected to study their interaction with certain surfactants: (i) *xanthine*: ethyl eosin, phloxine B, rose Bengal, erythrosine, 2', 7'-dichlorofluorescein, rhodamine B, pyronine B; (ii) *acridine*: acridine orange, acridine yellow, acriflavin; (iii) *diphenylmethane*: auramine O; (iv) *azine*: safranin O; (v) *triphenylmethane*: brilliant blue G, brilliant blue R, fuchsin acid.

The following surfactants were employed for these studies: (i) *non-ionic*: Triton X-100 (polyoxyethylene tert-octylphenol) (Eq-10), Brij-35 (polyoxyethylene (23) lauryl ether), Tween-40 (polyoxyethylene sorbitain monopalmitate), Tween-60 (polyoxyethylene sorbitain monostearate), Tween-80 (polyoxyethylene sorbitain monooleate); (ii)

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anionic : DBSS (dodecylbenzene sodium sulphate), DSSS (dioctyl sodium sulphosuccinate), SLS (sodium lauryl sulphate), Aerosol-OT, Monoxol-OT; (iii) **cationic** : CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide), CDBAC (cetyldimethylbenzylammonium chloride), CPB (cetylpyridinium bromide), CPC (cetylpyridinium chloride).

Anionic dyes' interactions :

Ethyl eosin¹⁰ : Fluorescence studies indicate that initially, both the cationic and non-ionic surfactants bring about a decrease in the fluorescence intensity of ethyl eosin, which is accompanied by a shift in the λ_{\max} towards longer wave length. Further addition of surfactant produces enhancement in the fluorescence intensity upto a limiting value. Fig. 1 shows the influence of CPB on the fluorescence spectrum of ethyl eosin. Addition of

Fig. 1. Influence of CPB on fluorescence spectrum of ethyl eosin. (a) 0.00, (b) 0.014 and (c) 0.030% CPB.

anionic surfactants do not produce any change in the fluorescent behaviour of the dye solution. On the other hand, the fluorescence intensity of the dye solution increases on the addition of ethanol alone. The intensity reaches an optimum value when the solution medium contains 50% ethanol.

The absorption spectrum of the dye solution also undergoes similar changes. However, the quantum of changes are smaller. The influence of CPB on absorption spectrum of ethyl eosin is shown in Fig. 2.

Phloxine B¹¹ : Initially, the addition of non-ionic surfactants result in an increase in the fluorescence intensity of the dye solution. Subsequent additions of the surfactant cause a decline in intensity which is accompanied by a shift in the λ_{\max} towards longer wave length. Brij-35 influences

the behaviour in a different manner; a continuous decrease, in fluorescence intensity of the dye, takes place on its addition.

Fig. 2. Influence of CPB on absorption spectrum of ethyl eosin : (a) 0.00, (b) 0.004 and (c) 0.050% CPB.

Cationic surfactants, initially, cause a decrease in the fluorescence intensity of the dye solution, followed by a shift in the λ_{\max} towards longer wave length. Subsequent addition of the surfactant results in enhancement of the fluorescence intensity. Addition of anionic surfactant has negligible influence on the fluorescence behaviour of the dye solution.

Rose Bengal¹² : Initially, the fluorescence intensity of the dye solution declines on the addition of non-ionic or cationic surfactant. Further addition of the surfactant results in an increase in intensity of the fluorescence. A shift in the λ_{\max} is observed in between the two transitions. The influence of Tween-40 on the fluorescence spectrum of Rose Bengal solution is displayed in Fig. 3.

Addition of anionic surfactants has negligible influence on the fluorescence behaviour of the dye solution.

Erythrosine¹³ : The fluorescence intensity appears to increase markedly on the addition of non-ionic surfactants. A shift in the λ_{\max} towards longer wave length is also observed. The influence of the addition of Tween-20 on the fluorescence spectrum of erythrosine is shown in Fig. 4. In contrast, the addition of cationic surfactants produces an initial decrease in its fluorescence intensity which can even fall to zero value. Further addition of surfactant results in a rise in fluorescence intensity reaching to a limiting value. The anionic surfactants do not influence the fluorescent behaviour of the dye.

The absorption behaviour of the dye is also influenced similarly. Fig. 5 displays the changes in the absorption spectrum of erythrosine that occur on the addition of Brij-35.

Fig. 3. Influence of Tween-40 on fluorescence spectrum of Rose Bengal solution ($10^{-5} M$): (a) 0.00, (b) 0.01, (c) 0.03 and (d) 0.3% Tween-40; (A) excitation and (B) emission spectra.

Fig. 4. Changes occurring in fluorescence spectrum of erythrosine ($10^{-5} M$) on the addition of Tween-20: (O) 0.00, (●) 0.005 and (x) 0.300% Tween-20.

2',7'-Dichlorofluorescein¹¹ : The behaviour of 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein appears at variance with other anionic dyes. Successive addition of any non-ionic surfactant produces a continuous decrease in the fluorescence intensity of the dye which finally reaches zero value. During initial addition,

Fig. 5. Influence of addition of Brij-35 on absorption spectrum of erythrosin : (●) 0.00, (□) 0.01, (x) 0.02, (Δ) 0.05 and (○) 0.2% Brij-35.

the cationic surfactants also bring about a decrease in fluorescence intensity but the same rises during subsequent additions. A shift in the λ_{max} towards longer wave length is also observed. The anionic surfactants do not exert any influence on the spectrum of the dye, except Monoxol-OT which causes a decrease in the fluorescence intensity.

Cationic dyes' interactions :

Pyronin-B¹² : Both the non-ionic and anionic surfactants, when added to the dye solution, cause an increase in its fluorescence intensity. The addition of cationic surfactants brings about a small increase, followed by a decrease in fluorescence on further addition of the surfactant.

Rhodamine-B¹⁴ : The non-ionic surfactants, if added continuously, bring about a proportional increase in the fluorescence intensity of the dye solution. On the other hand, small amounts of anionic surfactants diminish the fluorescence intensity, which again increases on further addition of the surfactant. The behaviour is apparent from Fig. 6.

The fluorescence intensity of rhodamine-B increases slightly on the addition of cationic surfactant but no significant change in the fluorescence behaviour is noticeable.

Acridine orange¹¹ : The addition of non-ionic surfactant brings about a large increase in the fluorescence intensity of acridine orange solution. Initially, addition of small amounts of anionic surfactants result in decreased intensity of fluorescence. Further addition of surfactant results in an increase in intensity. The cationic surfactants also cause increase in fluorescence intensity which is

Fig. 6. Variation in fluorescence intensity of rhodamine B on varying the concentration of DBSS.

associated with a small shift in the λ_{max} towards longer wave length.

Acriflavin¹¹ : The fluorescence intensity of acriflavin is enhanced on the addition of non-ionic surfactants. The cationic surfactants also exert a similar influence. The addition of anionic surfactants results in an initial decrease in fluorescence intensity which is accompanied by a red-shift of 10 nm in the λ_{max} . Subsequent addition of surfactant results in a large increase in the fluorescence intensity.

Acridine yellow¹⁵ : The addition of non-ionic surfactants causes an initial increase followed by a decrease in the λ_{max} of the dye. A red-shift in the λ_{max} is also observed. The anionic surfactants cause a large increase in the absorbance of the dye which is associated with a red-shift in the λ_{max} . The absorbance reach a maximum, and then fall slightly, on further addition of the surfactant.

The cationic surfactants have a marginal influence on the absorbance of acridine yellow. A slight increase or decrease in the maximum absorbance region is observed.

Auramine-O¹⁶ : Initially, on adding small amounts of non-ionic surfactant, there occurs a slight increase in the fluorescence intensity of auramine-O solution which is accompanied by a small red-shift in the λ_{max} . A large increase in fluorescence intensity follows on further addition of the surfactant. Similar influence is observed on the addition of ethanol to the dye solution.

Anionic surfactants also produce similar effect on the fluorescence spectrum of auramine-O. Here the magnitude of shift in the λ_{max} is larger. The cationic surfactants exert only marginal influence on the fluorescence intensity of the dye. However, some

surfactants cause slight increase in fluorescence intensity while others diminish the intensity to a small extent.

Safranine-O¹⁷ : The non-ionic surfactants display an extraordinary influence on the fluorescence intensity of safranine-O. Initially, in presence of small amount of surfactant a slight increase in the fluorescence intensity is observed, which is accompanied by a decrease in the wave length of the λ_{max} . Further addition of the surfactant is accompanied by a large enhancement in fluorescence intensity. Similar phenomenon is observed on increasing the concentration of ethanol in a solution of safranine-O. The influence of the addition of Tween-80 (non-ionic) on the fluorescence emission spectrum of safranine-O is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Influence of addition of Tween-80 on fluorescence emission spectrum of safranine-O ($2 \times 10^{-6} M$); (a) 0.00, (b) 0.08 and (c) 0.27% Tween-80.

During the initial addition of anionic surfactant, a decrease in the fluorescence intensity of the dye is observed which is accompanied by a blue-shift in the λ_{max} . A large increase in the fluorescence intensity occurs on further addition of the surfactant. The cationic surfactants exert negligible influence on the fluorescence behaviour of safranine-O.

Ampholytic dyes' interaction :

Brilliant blue-G¹¹ : All the non-ionic surfactants, on being added to the solution of brilliant blue-G,

increase its fluorescence intensity. The process is accompanied by a blue-shift in the λ_{\max} . The anionic surfactants behave similarly. However, the cationic surfactants do not display any uniform pattern.

Brilliant blue-R¹¹ : A large increase in fluorescence intensity is observed on the addition of either non-ionic or anionic surfactant. A concurrent blue-shift in the λ_{\max} is also observed. The cationic surfactants, however, do not show a uniform pattern. CPB and CPC decrease while the addition of CTAB or CDBAC results in an increase in the fluorescence intensity of brilliant blue-R.

Fuchsin acid¹⁸ : Cationic and anionic surfactants exert considerable influence on the fluorescence and absorption spectra of the dye solution. Addition of anionic surfactants results in an increase in the fluorescence intensity of fuchsin acid. Amongst the cationic surfactants, CPB and CPC lessen the fluorescence while CTAB and CDBAC enhance it. A blue-shift of 5 nm in the λ_{\max} is concurrently observed. The non-ionic surfactants also enhance the fluorescence intensity of the dye accompanied by a blue-shift in the λ_{\max} .

The absorption spectrum of fuchsin acid solution is markedly altered due to addition of surfactants. Initially, all the surfactants decrease the absorbance of the dye. The effect is least marked on the addition of non-ionic surfactants and maximum with cationic surfactants. The absorbance increases on further addition of the surfactant. Maximum enhancement is caused by TX-100.

Discussion

In the experiments made, it is observed that the non-ionic surfactants exert considerable influence on the fluorescence, and absorption characteristics of the dyes. Generally, these surfactants enhance both the fluorescence intensity and the absorbance of the dye molecules. However, the surfactant appears to exert maximum influence on the spectral characteristics of the dye when the surfactants and the dye possess opposite charges. This is due to initial charge-neutralisation and subsequent breaking up of the multimeric form of the dye to its monomeric form. When both the dye and the surfactant have similar charge, the effect is minimum. Even in this, the order of influence is : cationic dye-cationic surfactant > anionic dye-anionic surfactant. When the dye possesses both cationic and anionic nature, it behaves more like cationic or anionic. For example, fuchsin acid possesses both anionic and cationic charges on the ion, yet it behaves predominantly as an anionic dye.

A preferential interaction of the anionic dye, such as ethyl eosin or erythrocin with cationic surfactants, would normally be expected due to the presence of attractive forces. In such cases, the fluorescence intensity decreases and drops almost to zero level at a particular concentration of the surfactant. It appears that, initially, the interac-

tion between the dye multimer and the surfactant causes a change in the molecular geometry of the dye, resulting in inactivation of the fluorescing sites. The dye multimer, in its changed conformation, appears susceptible to disaggregation on further addition of the surfactant. This explains the enhancement in fluorescence intensity of the dye solution on further addition of the surfactant. Similar explanation would apply for the preferential interaction between cationic dyes, like acridine orange or safranin-O, and anionic surfactants.

Enhancement in the fluorescence intensity of the dye during the addition of non-ionic surfactant appears to be due to disaggregation of the multimeric form of the dye to its monomeric form. In the multimeric form, the possibility of inter-system crossing reduces the fluorescence intensity. The hydrophilic part of the surfactant would interact preferentially with the multimeric form of the dye. At low concentration of the surfactant, the dye monomeric-multimeric equilibrium can establish inside the surfactant micelle. However, at higher concentration, complete disaggregation of the dye molecules would occur. This explains, the often encountered, initial decrease and subsequent increase in the fluorescence intensity of the dye solution on increasing the concentration of non-ionic surfactant.

The shifts occurring in the absorption and emission peaks of the dye spectra towards longer, or sometimes shorter wave length, are due to dye-surfactant interaction in the vicinity of the critical micelle concentration (cmc) of the surfactant. A red-shift indicates the presence of attractive forces while a blue-shift in the λ_{\max} is indicative of repulsive forces. Both types of forces are present in the solution environment and the observed shift in spectrum is due to their resultant.

Some surfactants show anomalous behaviour. For example, Brij-35 and TX-100 often behave differently from other non-ionic surfactants due to the presence of ether linkage. Similarly, DBSS and DSSS may behave differently from other anionic surfactants due to their bulkier bidentate character. Presence of nucleophilic pyridine nucleus in CPB and CPC causes them to behave differently from other cationic surfactants.

The results described here indicate a pattern of action of surfactants during their interaction with dyes. More work is needed to refine the picture.

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